

Professional discourse: nature and change in online learning environments

Dr. Eulalia Torras Virgili.

Internet Interdisciplinary Institute.
Open University of Catalonia.
Av. Canal Olímpic s/n.
Mediterranean Technology Park.
08860 Castelldefels. Spain.
Tel. (+34) 93 673 50 31.
Fax. (+34) 93 664 19 70.
mtorrasv@uoc.edu

Dr. Elena Barbera Gregori.

Department of Psychology and Education.
Open University of Catalonia.
Rambla Poble Nou, 156.
08018 Barcelona. Spain.
Tel. (+34) 93 326 34 01.
Fax. (+34) 93 356 88 22.
ebarbera@uoc.edu

Abstract.

Students are considered to have learned when they are able to produce speech based on a concrete academic content whereas professional discourse should enable students to manage situations in professional practice. In this sense, professional discourse is more demanding than academic discourse. Our objective was to analyze the nature and change in professional discourse in the framework of online learning environments. Analyzing the nature of professional discourse primarily helps us understand the characteristics that make it special and that relate to managing situations in professional practice, and secondly, it lets us know which factors are involved in building professional discourse which finally results in being able to adjust online learning environments accordingly. This paper describes the results of an analysis of improved courses related to the construction of professional discourse. The main characteristic of professional discourse using ICT is that it is made up of a very small fraction of professional topics. The factors involved in building professional discourse are the type of learning activity, the kind of electronic content and task scenarios conducted. Regarding adjusting online learning environments, students expressed topic tensions and interacted as a structured professional community to solve those tensions so online platforms must be adjusted accordingly.

Keywords: *online, professional discourse, electronic content, Interactive-learning environments, professional communities.*

Introduction

Online learning environments are a valuable framework for analyzing the nature and change of professional discourse. They become a useful way to identify the characteristics that enable students to manage situations that arise in professional practice. Furthermore, analyzing nature and change in professional discourse is an increasingly relevant field in which there is still not enough research on. Sociocognitivism [1] weaves a theoretical framework that allows us to analyze professional discourse reflected in online environments. Specifically, the language understood as being both situational and historical, noted by Engeström, Engeström, & Kerosou in 2003 [2], is the key for analyzing professional discourse.

Professional topics and topic tensions

Research that deals with the construction of professional discourse in interactive learning usually takes the perspective of situational analysis. This refers to analyses discourse contextualised in the here and now. There are many more studies which only consider the development of professional discourse in the present. As Engeström, Engeström & Kerosou (2003, p.24) said “(...) in studies of professional discourse, we commonly make a distinction between historical analyses on the one hand and situated analyses on the other hand. Historical analysis implies a broad institutional and societal framework and a long time perspective.” Recently, the integration of both frameworks has enabled a more complete analysis of professional discourse. Professional discourse should integrate the historical and situational perspectives reflected on professional discourse topics. The topics of professional discourse can be identified from fragments. A fragment corresponding to a topic of professional discourse:

- When the fragment is similar in style to the remainder of statements and
- When the fragment is similar in procedure and
- When the fragment is similar in the kind of relationships between statements.

In order to analyze change in professional discourse it is essential to know the participant's discourse exhaustively. Comparing the participant's discourse at phases throughout the teaching-learning process in an online learning environment, change can be identified. Topics and topic tensions are manifested in interaction. Professional discourse topics can develop when tensions are aired socially, that is, participants said that they didn't understand a topic or group of topics or participants said that they did not agree with the significance of a topic or a group of topics. Interaction is the key to analyzing the change in professional discourse because it reflects those topic tensions as [3] Borko in 2004 and [4] Carabajal, Lapointe & Gunawardena noted in 2007. We understand interaction as “an interconnection of social actions that take place in a given scenario” [5] as Jonassen noted in 2008. All sorts of widely accepted interactions are taken into account [6] Swan, K. (2006).: student-teacher interaction, student-student

-
- [1] Tillema, Harm & Orland-Barak, Lily. (2006). “Constructing discourse in professional conversations: The role of beliefs on discourse and knowing”. *Learning and Instruction*, 16: pp. 592-608.
- [2] Engeström, Yrjö, Engeström, Ritva & Kerosou, Hannele. (2003). “The discourse construction of collaborative care”. *Applied Linguistics*, 24, 3: pp. 286-315.
- [3] Borko, Hilda. (2004). “Professional development and teacher learning: mapping the terrain.” *Educational researcher*, 33, 8: pp. 3-13.
- [4] Carabajal, Kayleigh, Lapointe, Deborah & Gunawardena, Charlotte (2007). Moore, M. G. Handbook of Distance Education. New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- [5] Jonassen, David H. (2008). “Beyond Discourse Dissemination: Learning to Solve Problems Online”. Michael Allen's E-Learning Annual, 1. San Francisco: Pfeiffer.
- [6] Swan, Karen. (2006). “Building Learning Communities in Online Courses: the importance of interaction”. *Education, Communication & Information*, 2, 1.

interaction and student-context interaction as noted by Kim & Hannafin in 2008. The extended work on communities of practice defines these communities as “groups of people who share a concern or a passion for something they do and learn how to do it better as they interact regularly: some communities of practice need to see others regularly, others are connected by e-mail, either way the community shares its practical experiences as a creative way to meet the challenges” as Wenger in 2004 [8] noted. Several indicators can be used to describe learning communities of practice as noted Cromity in 2009 [9]. Teacher-student interactions understand the game as a permanent interaction. People take positions, position themselves among others, and define their positions and auditoriums. Positions are gradually woven together from the various formations that appear during the teaching-learning process. In procedures involving computer-mediated communications, it is necessary to consider interaction that suggests flexibility as opposed to the rigidity of roles, which is more suitable for analyzing classroom learning environments. Construction of speech in cyberspace brings us computational objects that offer broad possibilities for being dealt with in a style that requires a close, tactile and concrete interaction. In this context it is important to detail the four research questions concerning the nature and change of professional discourse in online learning environments.

1. Which are the characteristics that make professional discourse special and that relate it to managing situations in professional practice?
2. Which factors are involved in building professional discourse?
3. What topic tensions does the participant’s discourse show in online learning environments?
4. What professional communities have these students developed?

Methods

Our proposal was to analyze the nature and change of professional discourse in online learning environments. To obtain evidence of this, we opted for a qualitative methodology as Van Dijk noted in 2006 [9] This methodological option was chosen because the research aim involved the process of teaching and learning. Experimental manipulation and strict control were not involved for several reasons:

- Learning must be considered in context.
- The process involved a rather limited time period.
- It is important to get direct data from the interaction among participants.
- The process was long and complex enough for it to not be reduced to a set of variables.
- It is important to maintain the naturalistic character of the investigation and respect how the process occurred.

Units of analysis

The unit of analysis was divided into three levels in relation to the four research questions:

- a. Professional topics of discourse. Topics of discourse were defined as fragments of text similar in style, form and procedure. The identification of the first level of analysis was conducted on the material in the teachers’ and the students’ discourse provided by various texts (scenarios, questionnaires, interventions in the classroom, messages to mailboxes and activities).
- b. Professional communities connection. The connection was described as one participant's response to a message from another participant. This second level of analysis was only applied to the participants’ electronic communications.

-
- [7] Kim, Hyeonjin & Hannafin, Michael. J. (2008). “Grounded design of web-enhanced case-based activity”. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 56: pp. 161-179.
- [8] Wenger, Etienne. (2004). “Discourse management is a donut.” *Ivey Business Journal*, January-February Issue. [online paper]. (http://www.iveybusinessjournal.com/view_article.asp?intArticle_ID=465)
- [9] Cromity, Jamal. (2009). “Value Continuum and professional online search services: The Collaborative Stage”. *Online*, 33 (4), 38-41.
- [10] Van Dijk, Tian. (2006). “Discourse and manipulation”. *Discourse & Society*, 17(2), 359-383.

- c. Professional communities positioning. The positioning was defined as the passage of a sequence of positions by establishing a set of flexible and permanent interactions. Consequently, this level of analysis was identified only in written messages between teachers and students.

Online courses

We selected and analyzed four improved online courses. In the context of an e-learning platform (Open University of Catalonia) we observed the teaching-learning processes. Each course involved a prototypical online learning environment activity. Activities were selected based on the three following criteria [10]:

1. Type of activity (debate and individual work). These types of activities are frequently found in electronic learning environments based on asynchronous written communication.
2. Choosing activities corresponding to electronic content (Educational Psychology and Political Science programs).
3. Task scenarios (questionnaires and real situations). We choose task scenarios to situate the students in professional practice conditions that had to be managed. The task scenarios consisted of professional practice situations that were very close to real professional practice and the students had to make an effort to manage these situations by applying the content.

Data collection

The data was made up of 404 electronic communications and activities written by 32 students. This data was collected to analyze the nature of and change in professional discourse in online learning environments. Students must have professional experience and extensive discourse of professional contexts. In other words, students who participated in the investigation had prior experience and specific training in the professional context of either educational psychology or in political science. The participants in courses 1 and 2 were mainly teachers (70%), the remaining participants carried out other educational tasks (school coordinators or teachers). All of them had a bachelor's degree or master's degree in education. The median years of experience in case 1 was six years, whereas the median of experience for participants in case 2 was 11 years. The participants in courses 3 and 4 were mainly politicians (80%), the remaining participants carried out secretarial tasks in local government. All of them had a bachelor's degree or master's degree in communication, law or economy. The lowest median years of experience was three years whereas the highest median years of experience for participants was seven. We considered that all the participants had enough professional experience (all of them are currently working) and educational background.

Instruments

Due to the diversity of the research questions it was necessary to devise different instruments to respond to these four questions. We designed four task scenarios presenting a simulated problematic situation that could be managed if the students used the professional discourse content in the materials. For the educational case, four-year-old children's problematic behaviour was simulated while a property conflict which affected a specific neighborhood was simulated in the political science case. We also designed four questionnaires that allowed us to record professional discourse and topic tensions. Finally, we created a database to record all written online messages sent during the courses, including the following different aspects: who sent the messages, who received the messages, date of the messages, time of the messages, mailbox used by the message sender, full text and documents attached .

Analysis procedure

We developed a protocol to guide three levels of analysis:

[11] Rourke, Liam & Kanuka, Heather. (2007). "Barriers to critical discourse". *International Journal of Computer Supported Collaborative Learning*, 2, 1: pp. 105-126.

1. Professional topics analysis. This level consisted of identifying the topics of professional discourse in the materials and documents produced by teachers. Two researchers analyzed all published material containing professional discourse that was involved in the teaching-learning process. To be sure that we made good use of the criteria, a procedure for inter-observer reliability based on the Cohen Kappa index was established (0.98 to 0.86).
2. Professional communities connection analysis. This level was applied to interaction i.e., all written messages sent to participants. Professional communities connection analysis was based in habitual social network analysis using UCINET (density, reciprocity, number of clusters and Bonacich's power index). Taken together, all these indicators characterize the professional communities (0.89 to 1).
3. Professional communities positioning analysis. This level consisted of establishing categories based on the data. This protocol was very open in the sense that we analyzed positioning as a range of permanent interaction. Before analyzing interaction, it was not possible to establish a protocol that included all the possible categories. Therefore, the positioning analysis consisted of inductive categories; thus, it was imperative to use a stable system that would ensure the reliability of the categorization. In addition, 10% of all the data to submit in consideration of the Cohen Kappa index were selected (0.72 to 1).

Results

First question- Professional discourse built with ICT was found to be structured around an extremely small portion of all possible professional discourse (between 1% and 5%). There were some topics, no more than five out of 163, that were used to build professional discourse. Otherwise students showed individual differences when selecting which professional topics to use. Students selected topics from material based mainly on two issues: topics had to be relevant for the teacher and topics were considered important by each student depending on their personal criteria. Students did not try to build professional discourse using the maximum number of possible topics. They did not try to write the most complete discourse.

Second question- Which factors are involved in building professional discourse. We obtained data about the type of activity, electronic content and task scenarios.

- Type of activity (debate and individual work). The number of discourse topics draws different profiles depending on the type of activity and content. Despite the increase in the number of topics that appeared in the discourse profile at the start of the course compared with the number of topics that appeared at the end of the course, this number differs depending on the activity. When the activity was a debate, a number of major topics came into play compared to individual work activities. The number of topics that we identified in professional discourses in cases 1 and 2 averaged 4.5 topics per student, while the number of topics that we identified in discourse profiles for cases 3 and 4 averaged 3 topics per student. When the activity was a debate, there was an increase in the number of topics that appeared in the discourse when comparing the beginning of the course to the end (63% case 1, 50% case 2). We interpreted this finding in response to the nature of debate, which allowed students to verbalize a more extensive discourse compared to individual work. The debates went through phases in which students introduced topics to reflect the meaning and use of the topics. However, in individual work, students selected a small group of topics that were considered the most relevant to the teachers and to the students themselves.
- Electronic content (educational psychology and political science). Each electronic content has their own topics. The number of topics that appear in professional discourse is different if the electronic content is educational psychology or political science. For this reason, we consider it essential to analyze each eContent to know how many topics are involved in each content. If the teacher identifies the topics involved, it is easier to help students assimilate and tensions are revealed in the topic.

- Task scenarios (questionnaires and real situations). If students responded to questionnaires i.e., they were supposed to answer questions directly related to the topics contained in the materials, then the participants showed more homogeneity in the number of topics included in their discourse. When students responded to questionnaires, in the sense that this was not applied and practical, we found the same percentage of fragments of explicit speech compared to the total (3%). If the scenario required the topics to be specific, defined and close to real professional situations, then the percentage of fragments varied for each participant with respect to the total (from 1% to 5%). There were more individual differences between the numbers of topics used when students responded to a scenario unlike the questionnaires. Therefore, topics were different depending on the task scenarios. According to the results, task scenarios must be taken into consideration.

Third question- Topic tensions are shown in online learning environments. Participants show topic tensions in cases 1, 3 and 4. Only in case 2 did participants not show tensions in their topics. Topic tensions are relevant in the construction of new professional discourse. For example, a participant said to their colleagues that he did not understand the real significance of a topic (educational psychology competence) and his colleagues debated the whole, more detailed significance of the use of competence in that context.

We found two kinds of topic tension:

- The first was when participants said that they didn't understand a topic or a group of topics.
- The second was when participants said that they did not agree with the significance of a topic or a group of topics.

When a topic was expressed as a lack of understanding students tended to construct the topic meaning. However, if the topic tension was expressed as disagreement then it was more likely for students to finish the course without changes in those topic. In other words, if disagreement appears during the teaching-learning process, it is more difficult for students to construct a new meaning concerning that topic.

Fourth question- **Professional communities are very relevant by topic tensions.** If students feel close to each other and the type of activity promotes interaction topic tensions are verbalized more frequently and the topic discussion are deeper. The characteristics of professional communities of students working on four courses were defined by:

- Density: The rate for measuring the ratio of existing shares to the total number of possible relations. Density is high (32.81% to 60%).
- Reciprocity: The set of connections ranging from one participant to another participant, is maximal for teachers.
- Subgroups: Subgroups depend on the type of activity; when the type of activity was a debate we identified subgroups, while if the type of activity was individual work subgroups were not structured.
- Power: The position from the acceptance of certain views or attitudes held by students and from the non-acceptance of other views and attitudes. Clearly, results show the power and centrality of all the teachers.

Graphical representation of professional communities follow:

Graphic 1: Graphical representation of professional communities: case 1 (education psychology), case 2 (education psychology), case 3 (political science) and case 4 (political science).

Discussion and Conclusions

Conclusion 1- We wanted to know about the professional topics in online teaching-learning environment. Main topic characteristic is the use of extremely small portion. This result has an important implication in the planning of courses to improve professional practice and the actions taken by the professor. **It is necessary that in planning the course and during the course, the professor asks the students to verbalize, discuss and apply the topics that are most relevant to them.** The teacher should address the differences that show students regarding the topics they want to discuss and respect these differences within reason.

Conclusion 2- **Topics that participants reflect in speech fragments are not independent of the type of activity, the kind of content and task scenarios.** The theory of action explains how professionals interact in organizations that construct discourse and how this theory of action limits these learnings. Therefore, this theory analyzes the construction of discourse related to types of activity. It provides relevant theoretical elements and gives great importance to interaction in the teaching-learning process and establishes the distinction between “theory of action” and “theory of use”. Theory of action is based on the fact that every deliberate action has a base that reflects standards, strategies and models of reality that have a general validity. Theory of use implies realizing these standards, strategies and models of reality in real scenarios. In the same way, the dynamic theory of the creation of organizational discourse is divided between tacit discourse and explicit discourse. “One dimension of this discourse creation process can be drawn from a distinction between two types of discourse: tacit discourse and explicit discourse. Explicit or codified discourse refers to discourse that is transmittable in formal, systematic language, while tacit discourse has a personal quality, which makes it hard to formalize and communicate. Tacit discourse is

deeply rooted in action, commitment, and involvement in a specific context". The author establishes two types of discourse according to the demands of context [11].

Conclusion 3- Topic tensions are important elements for defining professional communities. Teachers use to establish their position from the acceptance of certain views or attitudes held by students and from the non-acceptance of other views and attitudes. Otherwise, only 19% of students took a position during the course. Students can pass the course only focusing on specific topics but when topic tensions are express, students feel that they learn more. Debate compared to individual work is a type of activity where students tend to express topic tensions more frequently. In the case of individual work, students focus only on topics. **So, including debates in an online learning environment is important.**

Conclusion 4-The importance of professional communities has been evidenced by the results. The four cases were structured like formal professional communities. However, the relationship between the students was not the same in all four cases. In the four cases reported, a professional community had been structured, but, with the existence of some different characteristics depending on the type of activity and content. While in case 1, reciprocity was maximum (debate) for all participants, in cases 3 and 4 (individual work) there was a lack of reciprocity between the participants. Furthermore, the number of subgroups in the professional community varied depending on the case. When the proposed activity was a debate, there were a large number of subgroups. At the same time, there were no subgroups in the cases where the proposed activity was individual work, **So, it is necessary to design flexible platforms that make the students build different professional communities.**

[12] Nonaka, Ikujiro. (1994). "A dynamic theory of organizacional knowledge creation". *Organization science*, 5, 1: pp. 84-103.